

UHTS-LGTF

Quality Control Report

Mon Apr 29 03:49:22 CEST 2019

Summary

Run Date : 26.04.2019	Laboratory : Claus Wedekind
Instrument : HiSeq 2500	Library name : GC1
Run number : 0390	Ref. organism : Other
Flowcell : ACD4JJANXX	Protocol : Genomic_DNA
Lane number : 7	
Run type : HiSeq 2500 SR 125 cycles	

Notes :

- BaseCalling done using Illumina RTA 1.18.66.3
 - Post processing done using Illumina pipeline 2.19.1
 - For quality control purpose, each lane might be spiked with approx. 5% of phix genome sequences.
 - Adapter sequence not trimmed
 - Fastq file : contains passed AND not passed filter reads ; in header « Y » stand for « sequence is filter OUT ». Quality score is encoded in a +33 offset ASCII (Sanger like).
 - cf detail p.20 in https://support.illumina.com/content/dam/illumina-support/documents/documentation/software_documentation/bcl2fastq/bcl2fastq2_guide_15051736_v2.pdf
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Basic Statistics

Measure	Value
Filename	GC1_S6_L007_R1_001.fastq.gz
File type	Conventional base calls
Encoding	Sanger / Illumina 1.9
Total Sequences	199259674
Sequences flagged as poor quality	16388692
Sequence length	126
%GC	46

Sequence diversity ratio [GC1]

- diversity ratio (different/all): 0.36

Sequence identification

- **Adapters**

- **Mapping Results**

Reference	Reads processed	Mapped %	One hit / one genome %	Multiple hits / one genome %	One hit / multiple genomes %	Multiple hits / multiple genomes %
EMBLdb	10000	15.55	na	na	na	na
Human	100023	7.64	0.06	0.01	0.95	6.62
Mouse	100023	7.38	0.07	0.07	1.74	5.50
Repeat_db	100023	12.99	5.01	1.85	1.27	4.86
mitochondria	100023	1.12	0.00	0.18	0.20	0.74
rRNA	100023	7.09	0.11	1.80	0.94	4.24
miRNA	100023	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.20
ncRNA	100023	1.11	0.03	0.09	0.11	0.88
Other_ncRNA	100023	7.60	0.00	0.02	6.91	0.67
Plasmids	100023	9.92	0.42	0.00	7.56	1.94
Vectors	100023	27.02	0.27	0.00	5.62	21.13
Ecoli	100023	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

PhiX	100023	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00
Virus	100023	0.91	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.74
Adapter	100023	26.33	0.01	0.00	5.81	20.51

Per base sequence quality

Per sequence quality scores

Per base sequence content

Per sequence GC content

Per base N content

Sequence Length Distribution

Sequence Duplication Levels

Percent of seqs remaining if deduplicated 9.31%

Overrepresented sequences

Sequence	Count	Percentage	Possible Source
CGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTA	4794105	2.405958468044066	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 47bp)
AGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTATG	2646024	1.3279274962579735	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 49bp)
GCAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTA	1068994	0.5364828610529595	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 47bp)
ATACGAATAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATAT	450508	0.22609090487621694	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 41bp)
GAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTAT	371009	0.18619372026072872	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 48bp)
CTCGCTCTTCCGATCTCGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTC	357850	0.1795897748984574	Illumina Multiplexing PCR Primer 2.01 (100% over 32bp)
TACGTAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	346114	0.17369997303117138	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
CGAATAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	321274	0.16123382797464578	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
AACCAAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	240777	0.12083578938305399	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
CGGCTAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	237223	0.11905218714751084	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
GCCGTAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	221275	0.11104856068368353	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)

Sequence	Count	Percentage	No Hit Possible Source
CGTACAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTCCACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	218206	0.10950835942851136	No Hit
GTTCTCGCTCTTCCGATCTCGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCA	216991	0.10889860233335522	Multiplexing PCR Primer 2.01 (100% over 29bp)
GAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTATGCCGTCT	210599	0.10569072796937327	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 50bp)
TCTGCAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	209572	0.10517532012021659	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
CGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTATG	207698	0.10423483880637084	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 49bp)

Produced using part of FastQC (fastqc_v0.11.4)